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Call for Collaboration in Innovative Technologies 2022 (CIT 2022)

Pioneering applied
technologies

netherlands
eSciencecenter

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this call

This call for proposals seeks to transform highly innovative, fundamental knowledge obtained from advanced technological research into applied software technologies designed to have a substantial impact on research across all disciplines. The specific technology areas covered by this call are:

1. Digital Twins: Virtual Representations of the Real World;
2. SciML: Combining Machine Learning with Scientific Domain Knowledge.

This call for proposals is intended for researchers from

- a domain-oriented research discipline with a focus on technology development, or
- a technology-oriented research discipline (e.g. data science, computer science, AI),

who have a pronounced interest in making their research results applicable to other disciplines.

Projects receive in-kind support. This means that a team of research software engineers (RSEs) from the eScience Center will work together with the applicants to develop the applicant's (ongoing) technological advancements into a reusable, sustainable and fully engineered product, provide documentation, set up training events and help identify and connect to stakeholders.

A competitive proposal aims to deliver open technologies in the form of, for example, software libraries, algorithms, or methods, that potentially foster breakthroughs in research across all disciplines.

Based on the description of at least one concrete domain-oriented use case, the proposal must clearly outline the impactful deployment of the software during and after the research project. Commitment of project partners to sustain the software developed in the project is central to this call, as well as explicit support from researchers outside the project team to support, validate or use the software.

1.2 About the Netherlands eScience Center

The Netherlands eScience Center is the national centre for innovative software solutions in academic research. It was established in 2012 as an independent foundation and receives its funding from NWO and SURF. The eScience Center aims to bridge the gap between digital technologies on the one hand and scientific and scholarly inquiry on the other. Its vision is to establish a robust research community, in which all investigators in all domains are able to exploit advanced digital technologies and research software to answer innovative research questions, keeping the Netherlands at the forefront of cutting-edge international research.

The eScience Center employs about sixty Research Software Engineers or RSEs. As experts in digital technologies and methodologies, they may be seen as the equivalents of postdocs, assistant and associate professors, and top-level technicians at universities. In addition to their specific focus on the development of advanced research software, RSEs at the eScience Center will help applicants interpret

the results of their research and help make the tools and methods that emerge from the project (re)usable for the wider research community. They will co-author research and methodological publications together with members of the research team. Based at the Netherlands eScience Center in Amsterdam, RSEs perform their project activities both remotely and at project locations.

1.3 eScience Center expertise

Awarded projects are offered an in-kind investment in expertise in the form of RSEs employed by the Netherlands eScience Center. To maximize the added value and impact for applicants, the technological needs and requirements of the project should match with the expertise of the eScience Center. Broadly defined, the eScience Center's current areas of expertise include:

- AI: machine learning, image processing;
- Analytics: big data analytics, text analysis, visualization;
- Data processing: databases, real-time data analysis, interoperability and linked data;
- Computing: exploitation of hardware accelerators, high performance computing, cloud computing, combining simulations;
- Software quality: developing workflow technologies, improving software practices, advancing software sustainability.

For an overview of the eScience Center's expertise areas, see Appendix B (eScience Center Expertise) or <http://www.esciencecenter.nl/where-we-focus>. For an overview of the research software that has been developed and contributed to over the past few years, see software.esciencecenter.nl.

1.4 Available person years

The call makes available in-kind support by allocating to the awarded projects the time of Research Software Engineers (RSEs) employed by the eScience Center. The eScience Center's in-kind contribution is calculated in 'person years' or PYR, where 1.0 PYR represents 1,536 hours of RSE time available for the duration of the project.

The total available in-kind budget for this call is approx. 6.0 PYR. Applicants may request 3.0 PYR, so that a maximum of 2 projects is expected to be awarded through this call: one project for each technology area covered by this call.

Only proposals that are assessed as 'excellent' or 'very good' will be eligible for awarding. Proposals of insufficient quality will not be eligible for awarding even if there is sufficient budget.

The maximum duration of a project is 36 months. The eScience Center will allocate sufficient RSEs to carry out the research proposal. Note that when a project starts, the project structure as outlined in the proposal may need to be adjusted; this will always happen in consultation with the Lead Applicant.

In operational and administrative terms, projects are overseen by eScience Center's programme managers, who share responsibility with the applicant for monitoring progress and facilitating the delivery of project results.

Of the total requested PYR, 15% covers project management, line management, and organizational and professional development activities of RSEs (training, work meetings, conferences, etc.).

1.5 Validity of this call

This call for proposals is valid for proposals submitted before the deadline of **Thursday 12 May 2022, 14:00:00 CET**, until the Board of the Netherlands eScience Center has taken the final decision, as specified in the assessment procedure.

2 Guidelines for applicants

2.1 Who can apply?

Proposals can be submitted only by researchers employed by a Dutch research performing organisation. An overview of all eligible organisations is included in Appendix A.

Each proposal is to be formally submitted by a single named researcher (henceforth the 'Lead Applicant' or LA). The LA will act as primary contact for the eScience Center.

The LA must

- be in possession of a PhD;
- hold a contract for at least the duration of the requested project; in case the LA holds a contract based on a tenure track position, the eScience Center should be consulted;
- come either from a domain-oriented research discipline with a focus on technology development, or from a technical discipline (e.g., data science, computer science, AI);
- ensure a minimal personal commitment of at least 0.3 FTE per year to the project.

The activities of the research team, including the RSE(s), should be integral to the proposed project structure. Proposals supported by large research infrastructures and/or research consortia will be positively valued. Researchers employed by research organisations not mentioned in Appendix A may also participate in the consortium.¹

The LA is allowed to submit only one proposal in that capacity in this call. Moreover, researchers who are involved in a project awarded under the eScience Center eTEC 2020 or CIT 2021 Calls in the capacity of Lead Applicant (or 'Principal Investigator') are not allowed to submit as LA in this call.

2.2 What can be applied for?

This call is open for proposals in the following two technology areas:

1. Digital Twins: Virtual Representations of the Real World

Digital twins are virtual representations of real-world objects or systems. Typically, digital twins are based on a combination of several models, sometimes supported by machine learning, and refined with real-time data. Coupled with interactive analysis and visualization, this technology opens up innovative avenues of research, allowing for real-world modelling at an unprecedented scale and extreme levels of detail. Moreover, it allows researchers and policy makers to run what-if scenarios, supporting decision making.

Possible research topics include, but are not limited to:

¹ Employees of institutes for higher education (vereniginghogescholen.nl/hogescholen) may also participate in a research team.

- Model coupling and integration;
- Uncertainty quantification;
- Enhancing modelling and simulation capabilities with machine learning and surrogate models;
- Data assimilation;
- Interactive analytics.

2. SciML: Combining Machine Learning with Scientific Domain Knowledge

Combining machine learning with domain knowledge can yield models that work with less data, are more efficient in terms of computational processes and energy requirements, while they are also more accurate and more trustworthy. Moreover, an approach focused on capitalizing on domain knowledge can help avoid a well-known limitation of traditional machine learning methods: learning only from what they see. Combining machine learning with domain knowledge will make AI more widely applicable and attractive to domain researchers.

Scientific ML (SciML) seeks to address domain-specific data challenges and extract new insights from research data through innovative methodological solutions. SciML is explicitly not limited to the exact sciences only; it is applicable to all areas of research. SciML uses tools from both machine learning and scientific computing to develop new methods for learning and data analysis that are scalable, domain-aware and interpretable.

Possible research topics include, but are not limited to:

- Non-traditional / low-cost data sources, data fusion. Extracting Insights from multiple sensors and sources;
- Robust and reliable learning. Uncertainty quantification, stability, validation, performance metrics, and reproducibility;
- Domain-aware and physics-informed learning. Hybrid models that include both data-driven and domain-aware components;
- Interpretable / explainable machine learning.

A project may be requested for an in-kind budget of 3.0 PYR. The project duration should be between 24 and 36 months.

The organisation of at least two substantial workshops is mandatory. The main goals of these workshops should include technology development and user community engagement. The format and costs of the workshops should be negotiated with the eScience Center. Expenses of up to 30,000 EUR will be covered.

2.3 When can applications be submitted?

Project Proposition phase:

Applicants are required to submit a Project Proposition before they can submit a Full Proposal. The closing date for the submission of Project Propositions is **Thursday 12 May 2022, 14:00:00 CET**.

Full Proposal phase:

The closing date for the submission of Full Proposals is **Thursday 1 September 2022, 14:00:00 CET**.

2.4 Signed commitments

As part of the proposal submission, two signed commitment documents are required.

Project Proposition phase:

A **Letter of Commitment** must be submitted, signed by the dean or director of the institution at which the LA is employed, detailing the LA's minimal investment in the project in FTE per year.

Full Proposal phase:

A **Software Management Plan** must be submitted together with the Full Proposal, signed on behalf of an institute or other formal entity, e.g. a research institute, research infrastructure (GWI, ERIC, etc.), a research school and/or faculty. The Software Management Plan needs to specify how the sustainability (long-term storage, dissemination, use and re-use) of the research software during and after the project's completion will be ensured, and for which period of time. The submitted plan may be adjusted during the project on submission of a signed commitment superseding the previous one, and on explicit prior approval of the eScience Center. A Software Management Plan template is made available on the eScience Center website. *Note that it is crucial to involve an institute at an early stage in the process of writing a proposal, as well as to involve that institution in the project itself.*

There is no one-size-fits-all solution for software sustainability. Different possibilities and combinations are acceptable. Examples of measures and strategies include, but are not limited to, the following:

- the software is hosted by an institute and a user support desk is made available for a period of X years;
- the software is integrated into teaching in a course on a Bachelor or Master level for Y years;
- the software is integrated into a research infrastructure serving a large research community;
- a researcher or RSE from a research institute is allocated to the project to co-develop the software during the project, and to help maintain it afterwards;
- the software is integrated into an overarching software suite used in other (research) projects;
- a commercial partner is included as co-applicant based on a concrete cash or kind investment.

2.5 Specific conditions

The following general conditions must hold for all project proposals:

- An identical proposal may not have been submitted or awarded elsewhere.
- The proposal must match with the eScience Center's areas of expertise (see Section 1.3).
- Components (such as software, data sets or specialized hardware) necessary for starting or continuing the proposed research must be available at the date specified in the project structure outline in the application form.
- Awarded projects must commence within six months after the awarding date.

Furthermore, the following conditions apply:

Software and data accessibility and quality

The eScience Center expects a basic level of accessibility and quality for the data and software used in its projects. In all cases where existing data and software serve as starting points of the research, applicants must provide convincing arguments that they are usable. See the application forms for more information.

Data Management Plan

Concerning the management of research data, the policy followed by NWO applies. Responsible research data management is an essential component of good research practice. In addition to being safely stored and carefully curated, research data should be made available for reuse as widely and as early as possible. The guiding principle in this respect is: 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. In case data is collected, created or processed during the project, the submitted proposal must make clear how they will be managed and curated, so that they can be made publicly available.

A formal Data Management Plan must be provided to the eScience Center within a maximum of 4 months after the project has started. The Data Management Plan can be adjusted during the project but in all cases requires the explicit consent of the eScience Center. The eScience Center requests the LA to use one of several approved *data management templates*², to best match the details of the awarded project and/or any specific requirements of the LA's research institute.

Open Science

Open Science is central to the eScience Center. Open Science enables verification, reproducibility and transparency in all phases in the research process, and maximizes the chance for adoption, reuse and impact of outputs resulting from the projects.³ When writing the project proposal, the LA should be aware that:

- All source code will use permissive open-source licenses; research software developed by the eScience Center during the project will be licensed under the Apache 2.0 license. Software will be published in publicly accessible repositories such as GitHub from the start

² nwo.nl/en/research-data-management

³ nwo.nl/en/open-science

of the project, allowing community contributions. Software also will be made available in the Research Software Directory (software.esciencecenter.nl), so as to make the software findable for search engines, provide citation options and add relevant metadata (such as documentation and related projects, tools and publications).

- Substantial effort is put into making software sustainable. Preference should be given to extending, improving and strengthening existing research software supported by existing research communities. Developing new software should only be proposed when no other viable alternatives exist.
- Research data and publications are made freely available under open licences at the earliest possible stage.
- Reproducible research is supported (e.g. by using workflow technologies, computational notebooks, virtual environments, container solutions), so that researchers with access to the data and software are able to reproduce the research results.
- All academic publications resulting from research awarded under this call for proposals are to be publicly accessible immediately (in open access) at the time of publication.

Requirements regarding digital infrastructure

Applicants are asked to indicate the project's infrastructural needs (if any), in terms of computing power, data storage capacity, fast data transfers, or otherwise, and explain how they expect to fulfil those needs.

The Dutch national infrastructure includes facilities offered by SURF and DANS. For more information, it is advisable to contact the organizations and institutes responsible for these resources directly, in particular SURF (surf.nl) and DANS (dans.knaw.nl). Proposals may suggest the use of local, international and/or commercial (e.g. web, cloud, etc.) hardware and services. In all cases a brief explanation of the choice for specific infrastructures is required.

In case the project is awarded, any required access to the Dutch national infrastructure needs to be arranged by the LA after the start of the project using the relevant procedures. The eScience Center can assist, if necessary.

2.6 Submitting the application

- Applications (covering the proposal itself, the Software Management Plan, and the Letter of Commitment) must be completed in English.
- Use of the application forms (Project Proposition Template and Full Proposal Template) from the eScience Center website is obligatory.
- Project Propositions and Full Proposals can be submitted only via NWO's electronic application system ISAAC: www.isaac.nwo.nl. For technical questions, contact the ISAAC helpdesk (see Section 4.1).
- Project Propositions and Full Proposals must be submitted no later than the deadlines set in Section 2.3.
- As part of the submission process in ISAAC, you may be requested to provide additional information. Please take this into account with regard to the set deadline.

- Please take into account that the proposal summary provided in ISAAC, and the summary for non-experts, may be used for publication purposes, should your application be awarded.
- Please note that applicants should inform their employing institute of the submission by sending a copy of the Project Proposition and the Full Proposal to the director or dean of the department/institute. It is therefore assumed that the employing institute or university is informed of, and accepts, this call's conditions.
- Possible letters of intent from, for example, private partners should be added to the ISAAC fact sheet in a separate PDF file in ISAAC as an attachment to the application form.
- A proposal must be submitted to one of the technology areas mentioned in Section 1.1: (1) Digital Twins; (2) SciML. In case of doubt, please contact the eScience Center.

3 Assessment procedure

3.1 Procedure

The evaluation and selection procedure consists of three main steps. NWO will be involved to guarantee proper procedure. The procedure is intended to be as light-weight as possible.

Information Event

To inform interested applicants of the specific aims of this call for proposals, and of the role and expertise of the eScience Center RSEs, an Information Event will be organized on **Tuesday 5 April 2022 (13:00-15:30)**. In cases of force majeure the event will take place online. More information can be found on www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals.

Step 1: Project Proposition phase

The Project Proposition stage is intended to select the proposals that may proceed to step 2 (the Full Proposal stage).

The LA must submit a Project Proposition outlining the project ambitions. The Project Proposition should outline the technological innovations that will be transformed into applied technologies, describe what is needed for this transformation, and explain what the expected impact will be.

The Project Proposition should be submitted to the eScience Center using the appropriate template (www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals). The closing date for the submission is **Thursday 12 May 2022, 14:00:00 CET**. It is important that the LA should already make certain at this stage that all the conditions mentioned in Section 2 can be met realistically.

The project proposition will be checked for eligibility by the eScience Center and NWO based on the criteria listed in Section 3.2. If the number of Project Propositions is higher than five times the number of projects that can be awarded, the eScience Center reserves the right to make a random selection out of the pool of all eligible Project Propositions. Only eligible Project Propositions will be included in the random selection, should it take place. The outcome is binding.

All *selected* LAs / teams will be invited for a personal consultation session with eScience Center experts. In this meeting, applicants are given advice on how to best exploit the competences of the eScience Center in full, and how to best cover all eScience-specific review criteria.

Step 2: Full Proposal phase and assessment

Full Proposals must be submitted before **Thursday 1 September 2022, 14:00:00 CET**. The following procedure will then be adhered to:

Eligibility check

A formal eligibility check will be performed by the eScience Center and NWO regarding the eligibility of the LA, the correct completion of the template, the inclusion of the signed commitments, the extent to which the Specific Conditions of Section 2.5 have been met, and the presence of information required for a check of software and data accessibility and quality (Section 2.5).

Panel assessment

An assessment panel will assess the proposals. The panel will consist of acknowledged experts in applied computer science, data science and AI, and experts from the eScience Center. The assessment will be based on the criteria outlined in Section 3.2, and will also take into account the Software Management Plan, the Letter of Commitment, and the results of the software and data accessibility and quality checks. The assessment panel will rank the proposals on the basis of their scores. Proposals in different technological directions (Digital Twins and SciML) do not compete against each other. The ranking will be submitted, together with a recommendation, to the Board of the Netherlands eScience Center.

Step 3: Awarding decision

The Board of the Netherlands eScience Center formally decides on awarding of projects based on the assessment panel recommendations. The findings of the assessment panel will be sent to the applicants. This call aims to award one project in each of the technology areas mentioned in Section 1.1.

Timetable

5 April 2022	Information Event
12 May 2022, 14:00:00 CET	Deadline Project Proposition
June 2022	Eligibility check, selection, and notification
1 September 2022, 14:00:00 CET	Deadline Full Proposal
September 2022	Eligibility check
October-November 2022	Panel assessment
December 2022	Applicants informed of final decision

3.2 Assessment criteria

Project Proposition phase

To proceed to the selection phase, Project Propositions should

- propose a realistic match with eScience Center expertise areas (see Section 1.3);
- include a Commitment Letter signed by the dean or director of the institution at which the LA is employed, detailing the LA's personal investment in the project (minimum: 0.3 FTE per year).

Full Proposal phase

Proposals will be assessed by the assessment panel based on the criteria below:

Academic quality and state-of-the-art (34%)

- the proposed work should focus on, and aim to solve, a specific and urgent research challenge driven by at least one concrete domain-oriented use case;
- the proposal must indicate the technological and/or methodological challenges that need to be overcome;
- the proposal should discuss relevant existing technologies and methodologies and indicate why these do not suffice;
- the proposal must indicate how the proposed research is connected with efforts within the broader research community to address the methodological issue at hand;
- the LA should have demonstrable knowledge and experience in developing digital methodologies;
- the research team including the LA should make clear its availability for, and track record concerning, a collaborative effort, and argue why this is sufficient on the basis of a realistic project structure outline.

Impact (33%)

- the proposal must indicate which outcomes the projected software solution(s) are expected to lead to;
- the proposed research should potentially change the modus operandi in one or more research disciplines, in terms of broadness, scale, speed of result delivery, or otherwise;
- the proposal must indicate which efforts are made to promote the results of the project, in terms both of academic publication and of research community (demonstrations, posters, presentations, workshops, training, etc.).

Re-use and sustainability (33%)

- the proposal must indicate how the technology and software will find use beyond the proposed work itself, preferably across institutional, national or disciplinary borders, both during and after finalization of the project;
- the technological and software deliverables must be open source/open access and permit use and/or interpretation by other researchers;
- the proposal must indicate how the project will build further collaborations, in academic research, industry, or both;
- the proposal must indicate how long-term maintenance and sustainability of project results (in particular software and data) will be secured and managed.

4 Contact details

Specific questions about this call

If you have specific questions about this call for proposals and the assessment procedure, please contact:

Dr. Job Fermie, Program Officer NWO

Tel.: +31 (0)70 349 4478

Email: e-science@nwo.nl

For questions about the Netherlands eScience Center, or the eScience requirements for this call, please contact:

Programme Management Netherlands eScience Center

Tel.: +31 (0)20 460 4770

Email: open-calls@esciencecenter.nl

Questions about ISAAC

For technical questions about the electronic application system ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Applicants are requested to read the ISAAC manual before consulting the helpdesk.

The ISAAC helpdesk is available from Monday to Friday from 10:00 to 17:00 hours on +31 (0)20 346 7179. You can also send your questions to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will receive a reply within two working days.

The eScience Center adheres to NWO's Code for Dealing with Personal Interests (see nwo.nl/en/code-dealing-personal-interests).

Appendix A - Eligible organisations

1. Universities

Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam
Open Universiteit Nederland
Protestantse Theologische Universiteit
Radboud Universiteit Nijmegen
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen
Technische Universiteit Delft
Technische Universiteit Eindhoven
Theologische Universiteit Apeldoorn
Theologische Universiteit Kampen
Universiteit Leiden
Universiteit Maastricht
Universiteit Twente
Universiteit Utrecht
Universiteit van Amsterdam
Universiteit van Tilburg
Universiteit voor Humanistiek
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
Wageningen Universiteit en Researchcentrum

2. University Medical Centers

Amsterdam UMC (locations: AMC and VUMC)
Erasmus MC
Leiden UMC
Maastricht UMC+
Radboud UMC
UMC Groningen
UMC Utrecht

3. KNAW institutes

Hubrecht Instituut voor Ontwikkelingsbiologie en Stamcelonderzoek

Huygens ING

Internationaal Instituut voor Sociale Geschiedenis (IISG)

Koninklijk Instituut voor Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde (KITLV)

Meertens Instituut

Nederlands Herseninstituut

Nederlands Instituut voor Ecologie (NIOO)

NIOD Instituut voor Oorlogs-, Holocaust- en Genocidestudies

Nederlands Interdisciplinair Demografisch Instituut (NIDI)

Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute

4. NWO institutes (NWO-I)

AMOLF - Physics of Functional Complex Matter

ARCNL - Advanced Research Center for Nanolithography

ASTRON - Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy

CWI - Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica

DIFFER - Dutch Institute for Fundamental Energy Research

Nikhef - Nationaal instituut voor subatomaire fysica

NIOZ - Koninklijk Nederlands Instituut voor Onderzoek der Zee

NSCR - Nederlands Studiecentrum Criminaliteit en Rechtshandhaving

SRON - Netherlands Institute for Space Research

Appendix B - eScience Center Expertise

The Netherlands eScience Center has advanced expertise in the following areas:

Software quality

- developing workflow technologies: setting up an optimal and reproducible workflow
- improving software practices: robust programming to enable reuse
- advancing software sustainability: embedding software in the open science community

AI

- machine learning: using data to train computer models
- image processing: understanding patterns in images and video

Analytics

- big data analytics: exploring large volumes of complex data
- text analysis: understanding patterns in texts
- visualization: creating images to drive interpretation

Data processing

- databases: making data accessible and searchable
- real-time data analysis: processing sensor data ultra-fast
- interoperability and linked data: interconnecting data sets

Computing

- exploiting hardware accelerators: increasing speed at lower cost
- high performance computing: increasing computational scale
- cloud computing: easily accessing computing power
- combining simulations: replicating complex systems

For more information, see also: www.esciencecenter.nl/where-we-focus.